
Dichotomy Between Reason and Emotion in Human Relationships with Reference to D.H. Lawrence's Novel *Lady Chatterley's Lover*: A Study of human minds

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**Paper Received on 13-08-2023, Accepted on 12-09-2023,
Published on 13-09-23; DOI: 10.36993/ RJOE.2023.8.3.193**

Abstract:

This paper is aimed at easing the uneasiness of the tension prevails in the present Life situation. As it was rightly pointed out that the study of literature itself is the study of life and its principles, manners and values. The main reason for human tension is not understanding the "Differences" and "Dichotomies" which prevails among all human beings. The study of literature may enhance the understanding of the differences and it will help us to lead a successful life. This particular paper tries to unearth the root causes of problems in human relations. The need of the hour here is understanding the differences and adopt it to the life principles.

Keywords: Dichotomy, Emotion, Relationships, life principles.

The basic difference begins with an individual itself i.e., "dichotomy" between mind and blood or the "dualistic nature of the human beings which leads to catastrophe in their life. The following simple example may add some more fuel to this understanding. When we sit for breakfast mind will say 4 'idly but the physic, the taste of the tongue one may lead to 2 idly more which may result in diabetic, obesity and soon. (Natural Urge) All the human relations revolve around the dichotomy between reason and emotion. Here reason stands for civilization, industrialization, knowledge and intelligence whereas emotion stands for nature, relationship, love, hunger, angry, affection, sex and sensuality. The basic Contraction between mind and blood leads to psychological disorders, depression, murder, rape, molestation and mental disorder.

All most all the writers have dealt the dichotomy the one or the other way in their writings. These dichotomies affect the human relationship severely. Take for example almost all the Shakespeare's heroes suffered from these differences such as Romeo with his impulsiveness, Hamlet fatal flow is indecisiveness, Macbeth Tragic flow

is ambition, Othello with his jealousy, King Lear of self-delusion, Brutus with his faulty reasoning and Coriolanus - pride. The major causes occurred due to the dichotomy in the minds of the characters. With this introduction this paper intent to analyze the contradiction between reason and emotion in the human relationships which is considered to be the crux of human life, in D.H. Lawrence's *Lady Chatterley's Lover*.

An Introduction to D.H. Lawrence(1885-1932).

He is one of the great 20th century English novelists. He was a play wright, author, poet and journalist. He was an excellent student and was got scholarship in Nottingham school and college. He wrote around 12 novels, many short stories, collection of letters and little poetry. His best known novel is *Lady Chatterley's Lover* (1928), but was banned until 1960 for being over Sexual. He died in France on 1930.

Characters in the Novel:

Lady Chatterley- the protagonist,
Sir Malcolm father,
Clifford- Chatterley's Husband,
Oliver Mellors lover of Lady Chatterley,
Place- Wragby estate,
Michaels- first lover of lady Chatterley

Man and woman Relationship in the Novel *lady Chatterley's Lover*:

The very **first break** in human relationship, happened between Adam and Eve by tasting the fruit of knowledge and the extreme end of the strife between reason is fatal flaws and deaths or mental deaths.

Though there are many **Scientific studies** on human behaviours such as psycho-analysis, mind reading, face reading, astrology, the **interpretations of DH Lawrence** are interesting and mind blowing.

He says in his novel "The Plumed serpent" I am....

The earth and air I am lord of two ways".

Here two ways means mind and blood or reason and emotion. The present men and women are caught with this struggle, The strife between inner self and outer self. The self represents the power of Consciousness.

Again in the same novel, he says. "... **Your own singleness is your destiny. Your destiny comes from within, from your own self from you can only develop it**".

His writings are concerned with consciousness, the intellectual activities, mechanized civilization, **but deifying the unconscious, instinctual life of the emotional self.**

Therefore, the "**business of the mind is first and foremost the pure Joy of knowing, the pure joy of consciousness, the mind should not act as a director or controller of the self.**" Thus Lawrence faith is rooted not in mind and its activities, but in the dark, non-mental consciousness of the lower centers. i.e body"

The theme of the *Lady Chatterley's Lover* is **woman's submission and man's dominance** in their private sexual life. The Sexual intercourse is deliberately portrayed in the novel where women are compelled to acknowledge their inactive part as passive agents. Women are made up of high

connections and suffer from sterility of nothingness. Connie, the Lady Chatterley of the Wragby estate, a young lady with full of enthusiasm and passion, but suffers from dual consciousness and all her union with Mellor are purification, to bring her to the real self.

Chatterley's father was a statesman and army officer and mother, a cultivated Fabian. She had enjoyed herself as a student and had an affair with Michael whom she loved supremely and her love was only a minor accompaniment. She has never had a healthy sex-life being married to a man who went to war and came back with a crippled position during World War I. He became important, useless for sex-life. Connie wasted her being without any meaningful relation, Man like Michael, the Bond-street type, who have their pathetic two second spasms and not a healthy sex life. Clifford defrauded her body. Therefore, like all Laurentian heroin, she waited for a right match and says Ready "Wait! wait! She would sift the generations of men through her sieve, and sex it she couldn't find one who would do. Go ye into streets and by ways of Jerusalem and see if you can find a man (177)- Such a man was Mellor, her husband's game keeper. He looks like a self-assured, indifferent and free soldier. It reveals the dichotomy between the personality and performance. Thus this novel explains the theme of upbringing of woman's self in her natural submission to a right man in their "right relations". There is a recurrent assurance that only such an awakening to the natural mystery of human

body could save the world and men from the tragic collapse.

conclusion

The human race as presented in the novel is the world of greed which destroys all relations of men and nature. The Men and women in this machine age are only "**celebrating make shifts, mechanical and intellectual experiments**" (173)

Conclusion:

Lawrence through Mellor depicts the Man-woman relationships purely depends on sensuality and sexuality and not on over consciousness of money and social and political sides. Here emotion will always over rule the reasons. He says man on woman relationship is the core of human life. If I have a right relation with a woman (174). It is possible only when a woman conquers her modern woman's "dual-consciousness of making an enquiry into and stiffer from physical intimacy. Thus the central focus of D.H. Lawrence writing is dichotomies in the human nature such as body and mind, man and woman, sacred love and profane love, oedipal complex and electro complex, tradition and modern, love and lust, personal and social. His theories intend to teach the human being to get the perfect Singleness in the union of man and woman. He says, "When two beings meet, each one is pure Singleness, in totality of consciousness and in owners of being, they meet without negation of fusion but in the maintaining of the self's mystic balance and integrity.

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How to cite this article?

Dr.P.Pallavan “ Dichotomy Between Reason and Emotion in Human Relationships with Reference to D.H. Lawrence's Novel Lady Chatterley's Lover: A Study of human minds ” Research Journal Of English (RJOE)8(3), PP:190-193,2023, DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2023.8.3.193